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Abstract

In this work, basalt fiber reinforced polymer (BFRP) with enhanced electrical, mechanical properties and in-situ damage self-sensing capability was prepared using carboxylic carbon nanotubes (COOH-CNTs) modified BF fabrics via electrophoretic deposition (EPD) at different voltages. The BFRP with BF fabrics modified at a deposition voltage of 20 V (EPD20-BFRP) showed the lowest electrical resistivity. Compared with unmodified BFRP, the tensile and flexural moduli of EPD20-BFRP increased by 37.5% and 14.9%, respectively. Single-layer EPD20-BFRP exhibited a high gauge factor (GF) of 44.3 during tensile damage self-sensing. The acoustic emission (AE) signals during tensile and flexural damage process agreed well with the relative resistance changes (RRC), which confirmed different damage stages within loading process, such as elastic deformation, damage evolution, crack coalescence, and complete fracture. The multi-layer BFRP containing a single-layer EPD20-BFRP on the upper or lower surface of laminate exhibited distinct electrical signal responses subjected to the flexural loading.

Methods

Morphology

Mechanical properties

Damage self-sensing properties

Electrical properties

Table 1 The resistivity of EPD-BFRP in different directions

Sample	Resistivity ($k\Omega \cdot mm^{-1}$)	
	In-plane	Through-layer
BFRP	N/A	N/A
EPD5-BFRP	44.2(± 2.4)	895.3(± 9.4)
EPD10-BFRP	39.1(± 3.1)	600.4(± 7.0)
EPD15-BFRP	36.8(± 2.1)	313.78(± 3.8)
EPD20-BFRP	34.8(± 1.6)	233.4(± 7.1)
EPD25-BFRP	35.1(± 3.3)	247.6(± 1.3)

Table 2 Change ratio of the EPD-BFRPs mechanical properties at different EPD deposition voltages

Sample	ΔE_t (%)	$\Delta \sigma_t$ (%)	$\Delta \epsilon_t$ (%)	ΔE_f (%)	$\Delta \sigma_f$ (%)	$\Delta \epsilon_f$ (%)
EPD 5-BFRP	+9.9	+6.6	+2.0	+3.5	+6.9	+4.5
EPD10-BFRP	+13.2	+7.8	+6.4	+6.7	+15.0	+9.6
EPD15-BFRP	+23.8	+13.7	+8.4	+11.3	+19.4	+13.8
EPD20-BFRP	+37.5	+23.6	+13.7	+14.9	+28.3	+21.7
EPD25-BFRP	+27.4	+22.2	+14.5	+12.2	+23.1	+19.6

Conclusions

A BFRP with damage self-sensing property was prepared by electrical deposition of CNT. Single-layer EPD20-BFRP exhibited a high gauge factor (GF) of 44.3 during tension and 14.6 during flexure. For the functional layer at lower surface, the RRC increased linearly in elastic deformation and damage evolution stages. The multi-layer BFRP containing single-layer EPD20-BFRP exhibited distinct RRC responses subjected to the flexural loading on the upper or lower surface. This behavior can be used to identify the direction of stress applied to the structure. The results obtained in this work indicate that EPD-BFRP is suitable for in-situ damage detection of BF reinforced composite materials.

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